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PSYCHOLOGICAL STATUS OF PATIENTS DURING TREATMENT WITH COMPLETE REMOVABLE DENTURES.

Abstract.

The purpose of the study was to study the complaints of patients during the period of adaptation to complete removable lamellar dentures after 30 days of using the dentures. A survey was conducted of 29 patients who had complete removable dentures made regarding the quality of the latter, after 24 hours, 1-5 days and 5-30 days after the delivery of the dentures. During the examination period, the most common complaints from patients were insufficient functionality, difficulty speaking and chewing, and irritation of the mucous membranes.

Key words: complete removable denture, psychological state of the patient, adaptation to the denture.

An important factor influencing the success of adaptation to complete removable dentures is the personal and characterological characteristics of patients [2, 6]. Many authors [1, 3—5] attach special importance to its psychological component in the adaptation process. The process of adaptation to complete removable dentures is also influenced by the innate characteristics of the body [5, 6, 9, 10] and environmental factors.

The purpose of the study was to study the psychological status of middle-aged patients with complete absence of teeth.

Material and methods.

The study included 40 patients (23 men and 17 women) aged 40-50 years with complete absence of teeth in the upper jaw and partial absence of teeth in the lower jaw. The study used the "Questionnaire for measuring the severity of situational and personal anxiety by Ch.D. Spielberger (STAI, 1964) adapted by Yu.L. Khanina (1978), "Personality Questionnaire" (EPI, 1963) G.Yu. Eysenck in adaptation by I.N. Gilyasheva (1983), "Value orientations" by M. Rokeach (PVS, 1973) adapted by A.A. Goshtautas, A.A. Semenova, V.A. Yadov (1979 "Color test" by M. Lusher (1948) in adaptation by L.N. Sobchik (1982) with computer processing by A.Yu. Lastochkin and G.V. Kostyushov (1992). For the criterion of successful adaptation to complete removable dental dentures were taken to achieve from 0 to 4 points of denture hygiene and all positive answers from patients to all questions of the "Quality of Life Questionnaire for Patients with Complete Removable Dentures" A. Borracini. Results. A psychological examination of middle-aged patients was carried out at different stages of orthopedic treatment: before orthopedic treatment, in the process of adaptation to complete removable dentures and after completion of orthopedic treatment. Results of examination of patients using the "Situational and Personal Anxiety Questionnaire" by C.D. Spielberger, R.L. Gorsuch, R.E. Lyushen (adapted by Yu.L. Khanin) indicate that indicators of situational and personal anxiety change at different stages of treatment. These indicators are in-

creased before the start of orthopedic treatment, adequately reflecting the internal stress of patients with complete absence of teeth, but by the end of treatment they decrease significantly (by 30%). Middle-aged patients, who (statistically reliably) are more often married and lead an active life (family, work), are worried about the consequences of their upcoming treatment, because its outcome affects their social status. During the treatment process, having become convinced of its positive course, anxiety decreases, but its final decrease occurs only upon completion of adaptation to complete removable dentures. Results of the survey using the "Personality Questionnaire" by G.Yu. Eysenck (adapted by I.N. Gilyasheva) at different stages of treatment give ideas about the assessment of basic personal characteristics: neuroticism, extraversion, introversion; middle-aged patients show greater mobility of mental characteristics. In middle-aged patients with secondary adentia, social contacts are reduced, which is reflected in an increase in introversion in the psychological portrait. And since this often does not coincide with their temperament and character, an intrapersonal conflict arises, which is reflected in an increase in neuroticism. Before treatment, patients are withdrawn, tense, and nervous (parallels with indicators of anxiety and characteristics according to the "Color Test" by M. Lusher are clearly visible). But during the treatment process, changes occur in the distribution of results on scales from the poles of introversion and neuroticism to the normal dynamics of mental processes and extraversion. By the end of treatment, middle-aged patients with complete removable dentures again become more sociable, open to social contacts, and less irritated and nervous. Patients under the age of 50 prioritize specific (terminal) values such as "Love", "Good and faithful friends", "Happy family life", "Health", "Family", "Material well-being", "Self-confidence", "Interesting job". And these values no longer leave the list of preferences, regardless of the stage of treatment. Analysis of the dynamics of hierarchies of abstract (instrumental) values shows a similar trend. When considering the dynamics of psycho-emotional status according to the

“Color Test” by M. Luscher, its patterns in both samples become clear. Mobile, future-oriented, good and interesting work, material well-being, love, patients under 50 years of age change dynamically during the treatment process: from anxiety, fatigue, fear before treatment to an active life position and positivism after its completion. 16 middle-aged patients met the criterion for successful adaptation to complete removable dentures and 13 middle-aged patients did not meet the criterion. For correlation analysis, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient r was chosen (E.V. Sidorenko, 2001). In the studied group of middle-aged patients, positive correlations were revealed between the success of adaptation to complete removable dentures and indicators such as education (0.352; $p < 0.05$), employment (0.457; $p < 0.05$), marital status (0.423; $p < 0.05$);

$p < 0.05$), standard of living (0.389; $p < 0.05$), specific goals and values (0.711; $p < 0.05$). Negative correlations have been identified with indicators such as age (-0.312; $p < 0.05$), alveolar process atrophy (-0.322;

$p < 0.05$), situational anxiety (-0.488; $p < 0.05$), personal anxiety (-0.322; $p < 0.01$). Thus, indicators such as education, employment, marital status, specific goals-values,

which make the greatest contribution to the success of adaptation to complete removable dentures in middle-aged patients.

Conclusion.

Dynamic, flexible middle-aged patients adapt better to removable dentures, which is reflected in their assessment of their quality of life. Middle-aged patients who are married, have a job and good income, are oriented for specific activities that have goal-values in their value hierarchies, they are better adapted to dentures. A characteristic connection has been identified: low anxiety, high sociability, and focus on achievement lead to an increase in the adaptive capabilities of middle-aged patients. On the other hand, those patients in this group who are less focused on specific activities are less purposeful, more anxious, and adapt less well. These patients include those from the group who are not married and do not work. They choose less specific values among them and tend to “get stuck” on their own experiences and sensations. High anxiety, isolation,

and lack of goals and values lead to a decrease in the adaptive capabilities of middle-aged patients.

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